

ELECTROCHEMICAL CORROSION STUDIES ON FIBRE -REINFORCED METALS

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INTRODUCTION

In a previous paper (1) we reported a comparative study of the corrosion of pure aluminium and Al-Mg-Si alloy, with and without fibre reinforcements of alumina or silicon carbide. Corrosion in de-aerated 3.5 wt% NaCl solution was studied using double cycle polarisation (DCP) experiments and long term immersion (LTI) studies, as well as parallel gravimetric and microstructural examination. It was concluded that the major influence on corrosion of these composites was the composition and microstructure of the metal matrix where large quantities of second phase containing silicon, iron and aluminium were commonly found. There was no evidence to indicate that corrosion was accentuated by the presence of alumina and silicon carbide fibres, although the reinforcements did play a secondary role by acting as barriers to the growth of corrosion pits. In this paper we compare the corrosion behaviour of Al-Mg-Si (357) alloy reinforced with silicon carbide and with carbon fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.

Fibre-reinforced metals (FRMs) were produced by liquid metal infiltration of unidirectionally-aligned fibre preforms (2). Both fibre types were continuous, round filaments; the diameter of the SiC fibres (Nicalon, Nippon Carbon Ltd) was 15 μ m, whilst that of the carbon fibres (Grafil, Hysol-Grafil Ltd) was 8 μ m. We have designated the FRMs 357-SiC and 357-C, respectively, metal matrix composition and fibre volume fractions (Vf) being given in table 1. They were studied in the as-infiltrated condition.

Polarisation tests.

The double cycle polarization (DCP) method has been described and evaluated previously (1). Polarisation was carried out in an all-glass three-electrode cell with sweep rate of 20 mV/min. and using a computer-controlled potentiostat. The corrosive medium was de-aerated 3.5 wt% NaCl solution at room temperature, and each test was repeated at least three times.

Long-term immersion tests.

Open circuit potentials were measured on FRM specimens immersed for a period of 3 weeks under the same corrosion conditions as adopted for polarisation studies. Corroded surfaces were scrubbed using a brush or etched in 10% nitric acid for 10 minutes prior to further microscopy.

Microstructural analysis.

Specimens were examined before and after corrosion by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Electron-probe microanalysis (EPMA), with an energy-dispersive spectrometer fitted to the SEM, was used to identify constituents present in specimens and the composition of corrosion products.

RESULTS

As-received materials.

The microstructure of 357 alloy reinforced with Nicalon fibres (357-SiC) is shown in figure 1. Rod-like particles of almost pure silicon are present in the metal matrix together with white needle-like phases (platelets viewed edge on) which electron-probe microanalysis (EPMA) identified as FeSiAl₅.

The carbon fibre reinforced 357 alloy (357-C), figure 2, showed similar microstructural features, i.e.

silicon in the form of rods tended to segregate near the carbon fibres and long grey needles of FeSiAl₅ were present. Detailed studies, not presented here, showed evidence also for minor amounts of CrSiAl₅ and of Mg₂Si, NiAl₅Si₆Al₈ present as fine dispersions. The microstructure of the metal matrices of both FRMs is clearly quite different from the normal Al-Mg-Si cast structure in that the development of a characteristic Al-Si eutectic phase has been disturbed by the presence of fibres, a point discussed previously (1).

Electrochemical experiments.

A typical DCP scan for the 357-SiC composite is shown in figure 3; scans for the 357-C composite were very similar. Three potentials can be extracted from these data; (i) the corrosion potential, E_{corr}; (ii) the pitting potential, E_{pit}, and (iii) the protection potential, E_{prot}. We have found that the difference potential, (DP = E_{pit} - E_{prot}) is another useful measure related to pitting activity and, possibly, the area of the hysteresis loop (HA); these parameters are also indicated in figure 3. Polarisation data obtained for the two materials are summarised in Table 2. Some measurements, such as HA values, show a rather large experimental scatter but, despite this, HA values for 357-SiC are significantly higher than those for FRM-C, whether determined on a transverse or longitudinal section. The potentials E_{corr}, E_{pit} and E_{prot} are substantially the same for the two materials, although DP values appear somewhat higher for 357-SiC.

Long term immersion studies.

The open-circuit potentials for both materials were quite steady at around -800 mV(SCE), figure 4, i.e. they were slightly more negative than the E_{prot} values of 760-700mV, table 2.

Microstructural studies.

The corroded surface of a transverse section of 357-SiC after a DCP test is shown in figure 5. Deep pitting in the vicinity of fibres is clearly visible and such pits are initiated at regions of silicon segregation close to fibres. The plate-like intermetallic particles of FeSiAl₅ are little attacked and, in fact, appear to inhibit propagation of a pit. The manner in which the pits develop in the composite is better illustrated in a longitudinal section and figure 6 shows pits extending parallel to the fibre length. There is evidence also that pitting is associated with silicon-rich regions.

The appearance of the corroded surface of 357-C composite after the DCP test was markedly different from that of 357-SiC material. Many small pits are present but the dominant features are cracks in silicon-rich regions close to the carbon fibres, figure 7. These cracks appeared to be deflected around Fe SiAl₅ platelets, with little evidence to suggest the cracking causes damage to the fibres.

All specimens exhibited severe corrosion after LTI tests. A scrubbed transverse section of corroded 357-SiC, figure 8, reveals crevices between fibres and matrix and a thick film of corrosion product. The corrosion layer was essentially aluminium oxide and its thickness was estimated as ~ 250nm, using an EPMA method developed by Love and Scott (3). After etching, long thin cracks were revealed running between fibres and matrix, see figure 9, a longitudinal section of 357-SiC composite.

Severe cracking of a 357-C composite after the LTI test is revealed on a scrubbed transverse section, figure 10. The debonding which occurs between fibre and matrix, associated with this cracking, has caused bulging at the centre of the specimen. Considerable amounts of corrosion product are present as well as a thick (<250nm) cracked layer of oxide or other corrosion material. SEM of an etched surface shows sharply defined cracking around carbon fibres, figure 11, with the concave shape of the debonded radius exactly matching the radius of the fibres. These cracks appear to be stress-induced and are not deflected by FeSiAl₅ platelets which are split by them. Similar features were observed on longitudinal sections of 357-C composite subjected to the LTI test.

DISCUSSION

The nature of the corrosion in salt solution of composite 357-SiC is the same as reported for the basic 357 Al-Mg-Si alloy (1) despite the presence of fibre, i.e. microgalvanic corrosion. Corrosion of 357-SiC, which tends to start as pits at the fibre-matrix interface, is primarily due to silicon segregation on the fibre. The role that the fibres play in the corrosion process is one of inhibiting the growth of such pits rather than one of affecting their nucleation. Once the pits have formed they appear to propagate readily in a direction parallel to the fibres, figure 6, accounting for the large values of DP and HA. The preferential development of pits is considered to be related to the higher concentration of silicon along fibre-matrix

interfaces; indeed, in the matrix region where silicon is depleted corrosive attack tends to be significantly less.

Although similar results have been obtained by other researchers regarding the effect of the fibre on pitting susceptibility and corrosion morphology, different explanations have been put forward for the initiation of pits at the fibre-matrix interface. For example, Aylor and Kain (4) have suggested that the pits are associated with the formation of crevices in these regions, whilst Aylor and Moran (5) believe that corrosion pits are centred on the silicon-aluminium interface because this is a preferred site for passive film breakdown. Our view is that pits in this composite system are produced by the microgalvanic couple between aluminium and silicon segregated on the fibre surface.

The corrosion morphology of 357-C material shows the formation of pits between the aluminium matrix and silicon-rich second phases (figure 7) together with substantial cracking at the fibre-matrix interface (figure 11). Most reports on the corrosion of carbon fibre reinforced aluminium alloys agree that corrosion attack is greater at the fibre-matrix interface, although the explanations for this effect differ. The suggestions include (i) galvanic corrosion between the carbon fibre and the aluminium matrix (see, for example, 5), (ii) hydrolysis of aluminium carbide (Al_4C_3) formed by carbon diffusion from the fibre to matrix (6), and (iii) galvanic corrosion combined with hydrolysis of aluminium carbide (6). As regards aluminium carbide, it should be mentioned that such a phase was not detected in this work, despite earlier findings by Shorshorov et al (7) and Portnoi et al (8). This is, however, not surprising in view of the fact that the formation of aluminium carbide is very sensitive to the method of fabricating the composite and its subsequent thermal history. Thus we conclude that the extensive cracking which occurs at the fibre/matrix interface is directly attributable to galvanic corrosion caused by the electrochemical potential difference between aluminium and carbon, 1000-1200mV (9). The galvanic couple thus formed between aluminium matrix and carbon fibre encourages the penetration of corrosive solution along the fibre-matrix interface. The corrosion product which is produced, $Al(OH)_3$, causes internal stress because it has a higher specific volume than the aluminium matrix. Indeed, an increase of diameter in aluminium/graphite wire due to the build up of corrosion product has earlier been reported by Aylor and Kain (4). The stress results in cracking along the weakest sites, in this composite the interface between fibre and matrix.

Returning to a comparison of the electrochemical data we see that DP and HA values, as established from DCP curves, are larger for 357-SiC than for 357-C material. Since the magnitude of DP and HA values are considered to be related to the rate of pit propagation and amount of metal consumed in the test (1), it would appear that 357-SiC had corroded more severely than 357-C. It thus seems at first sight surprising that morphological examination of corroded surfaces showed that 357-C had suffered the more. However, the microstructural data show also that much of the damage in 357-C was in the form of extensive cracking caused by mechanical stresses generated during conversion of metal into corrosion product. This leads us to a final important point, namely that, as far as the general applicability of the DCP method is concerned, DP and HA parameters are of limited value if corrosion damage is largely the result of mechanical stress rather than electrochemical action.

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Table 1. Materials

Al alloy (357) matrix : 7.22 Si, 0.38 Mg, 0.05 Ti, 0.33 Fe, 0.16 Cr, 0.14 Ni, rem Al, all wt%
 357 - SiC, Vf = 50% : 357 - C, Vf = 40%.

Table 2. DCP test data : T = transverse, L = longitudinal section

Material	$E_{corr}(mV)$	$E_{pit}(mV)$	$E_{prot}(mV)$	DP(mV)	HA(μ coul)
357-SiC (T)	-825 \pm 40	-730 \pm 5	-783 \pm 10	62 \pm 6	155 \pm 70
(L)	-805 \pm 20	-740 \pm 10	-783 \pm 10	43 \pm 20	73 \pm 20
357-C (T)	-862 \pm 20	-731 \pm 5	-763 \pm 5	32 \pm 6	88 \pm 10
(L)	-931 \pm 40	-732 \pm 5	-770 \pm 10	38 \pm 6	31 \pm 10

Fig. 1 357-SiC; as received.

Fig. 2 357-C; as received.

Fig. 3 357-SiC; DCP curve.

Fig. 4 357-SiC; Potential change, LTI test.

Fig. 5 357-SiC, after DCP test.

Fig. 6 357-SiC, after DCP test.

Fig. 7 357-C, after DCP test.

Fig. 8 357-SiC, scrubbed after LTI test.

Fig. 9 357-SiC, etched after LTI test.

Fig. 10 357-C, scrubbed after LTI test.

Fig. 11 357-C, etched after LTI test.